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Water Quality Index and Human Health Risk Assessment of Class B Swimming Pools in Owerri Municipal, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Assessments of public swimming pools in Owerri municipal, Imo state, Nigeria was carried out for the purpose of determining the suitability of water for swimming in this fun loving town of Nigeria. Five public pools were selected by purposive sampling from more than 30 pools in the area. Water samples were collected in the morning and evening from pools and analyzed in triplicates for physicochemical properties and heavy metals content by using standard method for water analysis and Atomic Absorption Spectrometer. Data obtained were compared with WHO and EPA standards for drinking and recreational water and modeled on the Water Quality Index (WQI). Results revealed that pH ranged from 7.10 ± 0.02 to 8.1 ± 1.27 pH units, EC ranged from 40 ± 3.11 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 80 ± 3.44 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, COD value ranged from 0.08 ± 0.07 to 1.02 ± 0.91 , BOD value ranged from 0.03 ± 0.02 to 3.14 ± 0.13 , dissolved oxygen (DO) ranged 3.9 ± 1.77 mg/kg to 9.3 ± 2.41 mg/kg, suspended solids ranged from 6.43 ± 8.21 mg/l to 42.44 ± 7.00 mg/l, total dissolved solids (TDS) ranged from 22 ± 2.90 mg/l to 97.98 ± 8.79 mg/l. The major cations were below the standard. Nitrate ranged from 0.91 ± 0.02 mg/l to 0.96 mg/l, sulphate ranged from 2.34 ± 0.10 mg/l to 2.81 ± 0.11 mg/l, phosphate ranged from 0.34 ± 0.02 mg/l to 0.65 ± 0.02 mg/l while chloride ranged from 12.75 ± 1.89 mg/l to 31.89 ± 2.04 mg/l with mean 24.23 mg/l. Except for chloride, all other studied anions were lower than the permissible limit set by WHO/EPA. Concentration of lead (Pb), iron (Fe), Copper (Cu) were also below the permissible limit. The individual WQ indexes showed A (3.32), B (5.44), C (10.08), D (12.40) and E (9.77) with average WQI of 8.20 suggesting that the swimming pools are of "Excellent water quality", thereby suggesting

safe swimming pools for recreational activities in the study area. Values of exposure pathways for all metals at all swimming pools were less than one. Therefore there were no risks of heavy metals from the swimming pools.

Keywords: Contaminants, Model, Index, Permissible limit, Physicochemical

1. INTRODUCTION

Swimming pools are concrete tanks, large artificial basins, or large paved holes containing water for swimming. The swimming pool water should meet potable water standard by being a transparent, odorless, and tasteless liquid having a freezing point of 0 °C and boiling point of 100 °C (Cairns and Dickson, 1973). Swimming pool contaminants are introduced from environmental sources and swimmers. Affecting primarily outdoor swimming pools, environmental contaminants include windblown dirt and debris, incoming water from unsanitary sources, rain containing microscopic algae spores and droppings from birds possibly harboring disease-causing pathogens (WHO, 2006). Indoor pools are less susceptible to environmental contaminants. Contaminants introduced by swimmers can dramatically influence the operation of indoor and outdoor swimming pools. Sources include microorganisms from infected swimmers and body oils including sweat, cosmetics, suntan lotion, urine, saliva and fecal matter; for example, it was estimated by researchers that swimming pools contain, on average, 30 to 80 ml of urine for each person that uses the pool (Arnaud, 2016).

In addition, the interaction between disinfectants and pool water contaminants can produce a mixture of chloramines and other disinfection by-products. It was reported that sweat and urine react with chlorine and produce trichloramine and cyanogen chloride, two chemicals dangerous to human health (WHO, 2006). Nitrosamines are another type of the disinfection by-products that are of concern as a potential health hazard (Erikka, 2017). In accessing the quality of swimming pools, physical and chemical parameters are useful indicators. These indicators are affected by microorganisms present in the swimming pool.

Water is one of the most essential needs of man, both for food and for recreation. Natural waters are the major sources of swimming pool water. The quality of swimming pool water is enhanced by frequently changing the water and the use of disinfectant, such as chlorine. The highest possible concentration of about 1 ppm should be maintained because higher chlorine concentration irritates the eye. Chlorine based disinfectants; including chlorine, hypochlorite, and chloroisocyanurates are the most common water disinfectants for the prevention of water borne diseases (Bernard et al., 2006). When disinfectants react with organic amino compounds, disinfection byproducts (DBP's), commonly referred to as trihalomethanes, are formed. Organic compounds like chloramines and hypochlorous acid, are powerful oxidants, which destroy tight junctions in epithelial tissue and increase lung epithelium permeability (Bernard et al., 2006). Frequent exposure of these agents triggers the development of asthma and potentially allows the passage of allergens (Nemery *et al.*, 2002).

In order to avoid the problems of chlorine disinfectants, swimming pool operators prefer iodine as well as bromine. Swimming pool operators also mandate swimmers to shower with soap before entering the pool to prevent contamination of the pool. Despite these operations to ensure good quality of the water and maintenance of good hygiene, swimming pool could still be contaminated. It was reported that a swimming pool may be infected with pathogenic

microorganisms entering the pool directly or indirectly through contaminated air, soil, dust, rain water, sewage, human or animal excrement and individual bathers (Cruickshank et al., 1975). These microorganisms can affect the pool physicochemical properties such as pH, heavy metals, dissolved and suspended materials in the pool etc.

Unless the water is adequately treated, contamination may lead to outbreaks of diseases, such as skin ulcers, gastroenteritis, conjunctivitis, trachoma, ear infection such as otitis media, cholera, dysentery, eczema and skin rashes (Spivey, 2006; Font-Ribera et. al., 2009). These views have been shared by other workers Eggleston, 2007). Physicochemical and heavy metal evaluation has, for many years, been the most significant method for sanitary and quality control of swimming pools. For effective quality control, a test for physicochemical parameters is usually of primary importance.

In Owerri metropolitan, swimming pools are one of the recreational facilities patronized by different classes of people for leisure or pleasure in most of the hotels or guest houses. However, the swimming pools may harbor pathogenic micro-organisms from infected swimmers, from contaminated water source, from airborne contamination or from an ineffective treatment of the swimming pools. These may lead to contracting of disease both superficial or systemic body parts which the swimmers or bathers may not be aware of. Consequently the numbers of swimming pools are on the increase and information on their sanitary condition is scanty and water quality monitoring units are lacking in most of these pools.

Most pools are designed for recreational use and are not to be drained, cleaned and refilled after each individual use and may consist of elements, including, but not limited to, hydrojet circulation, hot water, cold water, mineral baths, air induction systems, or any combination thereof. Swimming pool does not include an artificial lake, a pool at a private residence intended only for the use of the owner and guests, or a pool operated exclusively for medical treatment, physical therapy, water rescue training, or training of divers (Lincoln-Lancaster County Health Department, 2000). Lincoln-Lancaster County Health Department divided swimming pools into six classes using A to F: Class B pool the concern of the current study refers to a swimming pool operated at a facility including, but not limited to, an apartment, a condominium, a property owner association, a child care facility, and lodgings such as hotels and motels.

Many studies have been conducted on public swimming in different areas of Nigeria (Indabawa et. al., 2015; Alfred and Mandu-Uwem, 2014; Ogbuagu and Esinulo, 2016; Onwuakor, 2017) and some areas of the world such as South Australia (Adrin et. al., 1984), Egypt (Abd El-Salam, 2012; Abdou et. al., 2005), Ethiopia (Yademe et. al., 2017), Ghana (Courage and Saviour, 2015) and South Africa (King et. al., 2010).

Indabawa et al., (2015) did an assessment of microbiological and physico-chemical quality of some swimming pools within Kano Metropolis, Kano Nigeria. The result of the study showed that the swimming pools were aesthetically unsuitable for recreational purposes. The authors recommended that efforts should be put to enforce effective pool water treatment by the proprietors.

Alfred and Mandu-Uwen (2014) investigated the pollution status of swimming pools in Akwalbom and Cross River Nigeria using microbiological and physicochemical indices.

Ogbuagu and Esinulo (2016), worked on the quality of Selected Public Swimming Pools in Owerri, Observed parameters which exceeds recommende bathing loads in several of the pools appeared to introduce many dissolved solids in water, and this in turn depleted residual

chlorine sanitizer applications, and so, encouraged the growth of coliform bacteria that were also introduced by the bathers.

Onwuakor (2015), carried out a study to investigate the microbiological and physicochemical characteristics of swimming pool water in Owerri. The identification of bacterial isolates was performed using standard microbiological techniques which included Gram staining and biochemical tests. The fungal isolates were identified using the needle mount technique. The physicochemical parameters analyzed were within WHO limit for drinking water quality except total dissolved solid with mean values of $380 \pm 10.0 \text{ mg/l}$ and $275 \pm 8.0 \text{ mg/l}$ respectively. The result showed that the swimming pools investigated were not contaminated with pathogenic microorganisms.

Yademe et. al., 2017, investigated the physicochemical and microbiological quality of public swimming pools in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. A cross sectional study was carried out from February to May, 2016. Nine hotels and one recreation center which recognized to have public swimming services were included in the study. The author concluded that the pH, residual chlorine and temperature value of majority of the swimming pools' water samples were within the acceptable limit. Regarding microbial quality, most of the swimming pools' water samples complied with the WHO standard. The authors recommended that swimming pools which did not comply with the standard both in physicochemical levels and microbial quality needs improvement due to their significant health implication.

Courage and Saviour (2015), performed a water quality assessment of swimming pools and risk of spreading infections in Ghana. Seven different swimming pools in Ghana were investigated for their water qualities and the risk of spreading pathogenic and antibiotic resistant microorganisms to swimmers. Result revealed that the swimming pools were below standards with regards to pH and turbidity. The authors concluded that swimmers in pools in Ghana are at a risk of contracting infectious diseases, hence urgent and effective mitigating interventions were devised to ensure standards. For the health of swimmers, finding a good pool water disinfectant is crucial. The water in swimming pools often stays in the pool for long periods of time. The water can get infected with harmful micro-organisms such as bacteria, viruses and algae by everything that enters the water. Heating up the water accelerates the forming of micro-organisms process even more. The mentioned methods of purifying swimming pools are found to be effective (Shalsabilla, 2020; Achmad, 2021; Igor, 2021; Ugbena, 2020).

Conventional halogen-based oxidizers such as chlorine and bromine are convenient and economical primary sanitizers for swimming pools and provide a residual level of sanitizer that remains in the water (CDC, 2009). Chlorine reacting with urea in urine and other nitrogen-containing wastes from bathers can produce chloramines. Chloramines typically occur when an insufficient amount of chlorine is used to disinfect a contaminated pool (CDC, 2009). Unlike many people think, these chloramines, not chlorine are responsible for the infamous 'swimming pool smell'. Chloramines also irritate the eyes and skin and are responsible for causing breathing difficulties. Chlorine water purification also has a negative effect on the materials the pool is built with. For this reason, the chlorine water purification for pools and spas is becoming more and more a subject of discussion.

In order to kill microorganisms, UV energy penetrates the outer cell membrane, passes through the cell body and disrupts its DNA preventing reproduction. UV treatment does not alter water chemically; nothing is being added except energy. The sterilized microorganisms are not removed from the water. UV disinfection does not remove dissolved organics, inorganics or particles in the water (Edstrom Industries, 2002). Ultraviolet light systems

tremendously reduce chloramines concentrations and inactivates micro-organisms such as the parasitic protozoans *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia lamblia*, which are resistant to chlorine. That's why UV-C can be used as main disinfectant with chlorine for example as oxidiser, as UV light does not impart a residual disinfectant to the pool water. While ozone oxidizes, UV disinfects so when used together it can drastically reduce the amount of chlorine. It's for a good reason that people call this Advanced Oxidation Process (AOP), the next big thing' in pool water sanitation (Arjan, 2017).

The research was aimed to ascertain the water quality index (WQI) of some swimming pools in Owerri metropolis so as to bring into light and reduce the risks of contracting disease in order to stem the incidence of recreational disease. The objectives include: to determination of physico-chemical parameters before use; to compare the physicochemical properties with Standard Organisation of Nigeria (SON) for potable water quality; to use the Water Quality Index model on the physicochemical properties and ascertain its quality; to calculate the water quality index for other researches and compare with present study.

The study should provide information on the status of water quality swimming pools in Owerri metropolis. The study also gives the management of the selected hotels an insight on the quality of their swimming pools and possible ways to regulate it, reduces large data into simple understandable figure for easy action plan. The study covers the physicochemical parameters such as pH, temperature, dissolved oxygen, suspended and dissolved solids, anions, cations and heavy metals. The results obtained were subjected to WQI model for its quality assessment.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study Area

This study was carried out in Owerri, Imo State. The area is located between latitude $5^{\circ}15'$ and $5^{\circ}34'$ N, Longitude $7^{\circ}15'$ - $7^{\circ}30'$ E. Owerri North is in the tropical rainforest zone and has two distinct season; the wet and the dry seasons. The wet season starts from April through October with peak occurrence between June and September while dry season commences in November through March annually. It has annual rainfall of 2,250 mm-2,500 mm with the relative humidity of about 70-80% and mean temperature of 27 °C. Owerri North has a projected population of 176,334 (Census, 2006) and harbors three higher institutions. As a result of the recent growth in population, the existing social amenities including water supply sources, sewage disposal etc has been affected negatively.

2. 2. Hydrology of Owerri

The study area is underlain by Benin formation of Miocene to recent age. This constitutes the sedimentary formation which contains the aquifers. The geology controls the occurrence and type of aquifers. The underlying Benin formation consists of thick unconsolidated sand mixed with clay sand lenses. The sand and clay intercalations constitute a system of aquifer separated by aquitards. Boreholes penetrating the upper 200m of the area reveal the existence of three aquifer systems. Medium to coarse grain, to sub-angular sand forms the aquifers, whereas the clay and clayey fine grained sands form the aquitards. The upper is unconfined and is present throughout the area. The porous materials are medium to coarse grained sands. The middle aquifer is semi-confined to confined, and has a thickness range of 30m-40m. The aquifer

is extensively tapped by boreholes. The aquitard separating the aquifers is made up of 3m-15m thick sandy clay. The aquitard has a high leakage factor. Recharge occurs from rainfall and surface flow (Uma, 1984).

2. 3. Methodology

2. 3. 1. Sample collection

Five samples were collected from five different swimming pools in Owerri. The samples were labeled according to the name of the hotels where the pools are located (A to E). The water samples were collected during the rainy season period (April-May). At each sampling point, 5 composite samples were collected and pooled as a sample. These sampling points were at least 10m apart and sampling was done in the morning. Clean plastic bottles were used for the collection.

Figure 1. Map showing Owerri municipal and sample area

2. 3. 2. Measurement of physicochemical parameters of water

2. 3. 2. 1. Electrical Conductivity (EC) ($\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$)

The electrical conductivity was measured using HANNA HI8733 EC METER in $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$. Calibrated using KCl. The EC probe is then introduced into the water sample for 60seconds and readings is taken.

2. 3. 2. 2. pH

The pH was determined using JENWAY 3510pH METER which was calibrated using buffer 4 and buffer 7 by dissolving one capsule each in 100 ml of distilled water respectively. The pH was determined also with the same method used for the EC measurement.

2. 3. 2. 3. Dissolved Oxygen

Dissolved oxygen concentration of the water samples was determined with a Jen-way 9071 digital oxygen analyzer by inserting the probe into the water samples.

2. 3. 2. 4. Biological Oxygen Demand

Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD_5) was analyzed through iodometric titrations using Winkler's reagent, sulphuric acid, starch indicator and sodium thiosulphate.

$$\text{BOD} \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{l}} \right) = \text{DO}_1 - \text{DO}_5 \quad (1)$$

where; DO_1 = initial dissolved oxygen (immediately after sampling preparation) DO_5 = final dissolved oxygen (after 5 days of incubation)

Figure 2. Photographs of some typical swimming pools studied

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2. 3. 3. 5. Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)

Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) was determined using potassium dichromate digestion method. Organic substances in the samples were completely oxidized (using potassium dichromate $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$) and the remaining dichromate was determined by titration with ferrous ammonium sulphate. Silver sulphate was added as a catalyst for the oxidation and mercuric sulphate was added to overcome chloride interference.

$$\text{COD} (\text{mgO}/\text{l}) = (A - B) \times M \times 8000 \quad (2)$$

2. 3. 3. 6. TSS (Total Suspended Solid) (mg/l)

Three filters were rinsed with 20-30 ml De-ionized water to remove any solids that may remain from the manufacturing process. The filters were placed in separate, labeled aluminum weighed pans, then dried in a 104°C oven for 30 minutes, then they (filter and pan) were placed in a desiccator, and a constant weight was obtained by repeating the oven and desiccation steps. 100 ml of sample was filtered through each pre-weighed filter. Each paper was placed in its aluminum weighed pan in the 104°C oven for 1 hour. Cool the filter and pan in a desiccator and a constant weight was obtained by repeating the drying and desiccation steps.

Calculation:

$$TSS \left(\frac{mg}{l} \right) = \frac{(Average\ final\ weighting - Average\ initial\ weight) \times 1000\ mg/l}{Samples\ volume\ in\ L} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

2. 3. 3. 7. Phosphate (PO₄³⁻) (mg/l)

The phosphorus was determined by the vanadate colorimetric method. The phosphorus was determined as phosphate by the vanadium phosphomolybdate (Vanadate) colorimetric method in which the phosphorus present as the orthophosphate reacts with a vanadate-molybdate reagent to produce a yellow complex, the absorbance reagent of which is measured 420nm.

2. 3. 3. 8. Nitrate (NO₃²⁻) (mg/l)

One test tube was rinsed and filled to the 2.5 ml with water from the sample bottle. Then it was diluted to 5 ml with the Mixed Acid Reagent. Capped and mixed. Then it was allowed to stand for 2 minutes. Using 0.1 g spoon to add one level measure (avoided any 50-60 times in one minute) for 10 minutes. Then the test tubes were inserted into the Nitrate Nitrogen Comparator. The sample colors were matched to the color standard. The results were recorded as mg/l(ppm).

2. 3. 3. 9. Chloride

Chloride was done using argentometric method according to EPA method 9253.50 ml of the sample was collected and poured into a white porcelain container. Approximately 1.0 ml of K₂CrO₄ indicator solution was added and mix. Then, standard AgNO₃ solution was added dropwise from a 25 ml burette until the orange color persisted throughout the sample. The procedure described was repeated using exactly one-half as much original sample, diluted to 50 ml with halide-free water. Throughout the experiment H₂O₂ was added and mixed for 1 min to stop the reaction of sulfide ion.

The chloride was calculated as

$$Cl(mg/l) = \frac{[(V_1 - V_2) \times N \times 71]}{S} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

where V₁ = Milliliters of standard AgNO₃ solution added in titrating the sample prepared V₂ = Milliliters of standard AgNO₃ solution added in titrating the sample prepared from halide-free water, N = Normality of standard AgNO₃ solution. S = Milliliters of original sample (50 ml test sample), 71 = 2×35.5 mg Cl /equivalent.

2. 3. 3. 10. Determination of Metals and macro elements:

The water sample was digested using aqua-regia. 1 ml of the water sample was weighed into a test tube and was digested with 24 ml of aqua-regia for 3days. The supernatant is then filtered using a sieve. The concentrations of Na, K, Mg, Ca, Mn, Pb, Cd, Fe, Zn, and Cu in the respective water samples were then determined using Perkins Elmer AAnalyst 400 Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer.

2. 4. Data Analysis

Experiments were conducted in triplicate and reported as mean and standard deviation. Basic descriptive statistics was conducted to minimum, maximum and mean values. Graphs were also used where applicable.

2. 4. 1. Water Quality Index (WQI)

Water Quality Index (WQI) is normally used for water suitability for consumption but it was calculated here based on studied physicochemical parameters with a view of determining the suitability of the swimming pools for swimming. WQI gives a single number which characterizes the overall quality of the water. WQI was computed using equation (5)

$$WQI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n q_i \cdot W_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i} \quad (5)$$

where: W_i is weight age factor (calculated from equation 7), K is a constant value and it is calculated using equation (6)

$$K = \frac{1}{\sum(\frac{1}{S_i})} \quad (6);$$

S_i is the standard value of the i^{th} water quality parameter; n is the total number of water quality parameters;

$$W_i = \frac{K}{S_i} \quad (7)$$

q_i is the quality rating for the i^{th} water quality parameter and is calculated using the equation (8)

$$q_i = \frac{C_m - V_i}{S_i - V_i} \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

where: V_i - ideal value for pure water and it's 0 for all parameters except pH (7.0) and DO (14.6 mg/l).

The ranking for WQI was categorized according to Verla *et. al.*, (2018); Enyoh *et. al.*, (2018) but edited for the purpose of the study as follows: WQI < 50- Excellent water quality (EWQ); 50 < WQI ≤ 100- Good water quality (GWQ); 100 < WQI ≤ 200- Poor water quality (PWQ) - 200 < WQI ≤ 300- Very poor water quality and WQI > 300- Unsuitable for swimming

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Physicochemical analysis

The results for the physicochemical analysis of the studied swimming pools are presented in the table 1.

Table 1. Mean values of physicochemical properties of water from swimming pools in Owerri.

Parameter	A	B	C	D	E	Min	Max	Mean	Standard
Appearance	Clear	Clear	Clear	Clear	Slightly cloudy	- Clear			
Colour	Colourless	Colourless	Colourless	Colourless	Colourless	-	-	-	Colourless
pH	7.90±0.05	7.10±0.02	7.60±1.01	7.78±0.05	8.1±1.27	7.10	8.1	7.70	7-7.8*
Temp. (°C)	27.2±0.01	26.9±0.02	27.2±0.12	27.0±0.53	27.6±0.89	27.0	27.6	27.18	22-26*
EC	40 ±3.11	44±2.01	43±1.01	56±2.31	80±3.44	40	80	52.60	1000*
BOD	0.03±0.02	1.42±1.01	1.49±1.13	2.54±0.09	3.14±0.13	0.03	3.14	1.72	1-2*
COD	1.02 ±0.91	0.08±0.07	0.062 ±0.01	0.048 ±0.01	0.072±0.02	0.08	1.02	0.26	N/A
DO (mg/kg)	6.8±1.20	3.9±1.77	4.1±0.99	3.2±1.43	9.3±2.41	3.9	9.3	5.46	9-10*
TDS (mg/l)	23.94±5.8	23.84±6.8	43.78±2.49	22±2.90	97.98±8.79	22	97.98	42.31	500*
TSS	7.74±4.97	6.64±3.09	19.74±2.44	6.43±8.21	42.44±7.00	6.43	42.44	16.60	50 ⁺
Na ⁺ (mg/l)	0.33±0.01	0.67±0.01	0.37±0.01	0.30±0.01	0.37±0.01	0.30	0.67	0.41	N/A
K ⁺ (mg/l)	0.89±0.02	0.79±0.01	0.88±0.01	0.19±0.00	0.82±0.01	0.19	0.89	0.71	N/A
Mg ²⁺ (mg/l)	0.03±0.10	0.08±0.10	0.07±0.11	0.12±0.10	0.03±0.01	0.03	0.12	0.07	0.5 ⁺
Ca ²⁺ (mg/l)	0.02±0.10	0.06±0.10	0.08±0.10	0.05±0.10	0.02±0.10	0.02	0.08	0.05	70 ⁺
Cu (mg/l)	0.03±0.01	0.07±0.01	0.07±0.01	0.003±0.01	0.16±0.01	0.003	0.16	0.07	0.3 ⁺
Cd (mg/l)	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.003 ⁺
Mn(mg/l)	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.4 ⁺
Zn (mg/l)	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	<0.1 ⁺
Fe (mg/l)	ND	0.003±0.0	0.002±0.00	ND	0.001±0.00	0.001	0.003	0.001	0.3 ⁺

Pb(mg/l)	ND	ND	0.001±0.00	0.002±0.00	0.001±0.01	ND	0.002	0.001	0.01 ⁺
Nitrate (mg/l)	0.96±0.02	0.91±0.02	0.92±0.02	0.91±0.02	0.92±0.02	0.91	0.96	0.92	1-5*
Sulphate (mg/l)	2.81±0.11	2.34±0.10	2.48±0.12	2.39±0.12	2.48±0.12	2.34	2.81	2.50	250 ⁺
Phosphate (mg/l)	0.37±0.02	0.65±0.02	0.36±0.02	0.34±0.02	0.37±0.02	0.34	0.65	0.42	1-10*
Chlorides (mg/l)	12.75±1.9	20.74±2.13	30.90±1.03	31.89±2.04	24.85±1.97	12.8	31.89	24.23	1-3*

Key; A-Ibis Royal, B-Immaculate Hotel, C-Villa Garden, D-Concord Hotel, E- Heroes Apartment; + WHO (2007), * WHO and EPA Standard for recreational waters reported by Indabawa *et. al.*, (2015).

The distribution of various physicochemical parameters studied on the swimming pool water samples are presented in Figures 3–14. The distributions enable easy comparison of results obtained for the different pools in Owerri municipal.

Figure 3. Distribution of pH

Figure 4. Distribution of temperature

Figure 5. Distribution of EC

Figure 6. Distribution of BOD

Figure 7. Distribution of COD

Figure 8. Distribution of DO

Figure 9. Distribution of TDS

Figure 10. Distribution of TSS

Figure 11. Distribution of major cations

Figure 12. Distribution of sulphates

Figure 13. Distribution of phosphate

Figure 14. Distribution of chlorides

Table 2. Computed Water Quality Index (WQI) for the swimming pools water samples.

Property	W _i	Water samples									
		A		B		C		D		E	
		q _i	q _i W _i								
Ph	0.00028	112.5	0.03	12.5	0.0035	75	0.021	97.5	0.027	137.5	0.039
Temp.	0.00008	104.62	0.0088	103.46	0.0087	104.62	0.0088	103.85	0.0087	106.15	0.0089
EC	0.000002	4	8.76E-6	4.4	9.64E-6	4.3	9.42E-6	5.6	1.23E-5	8	1.75E-5
BOD	0.001095	1.5	1.64E-3	71	0.078	74.5	0.082	127	0.14	157	0.17
DO	0.000219	180	0.039	252.5	0.055	247.5	0.054	270	0.059	117.5	0.026
TDS	0.000004	4.79	2.09E-5	4.77	2.08E-5	8.76	3.84E-5	4.4	1.93E-5	19.60	8.58E-6
TSS	0.000044	15.48	6.78E-4	13.28	5.82E-4	39.48	1.73E-3	12.86	5.63E-4	84.88	3.72E-3
Mg ²⁺	0.001095	6	6.57E-3	16	0.018	14	0.015	24	0.026	6	6.57E-3
Ca ²⁺	0.000031	0.03	9.39E-7	0.09	2.82E-6	0.11	3.44E-6	0.07	2.19E-6	0.03	9.39E-7
Cu	0.0073	10	0.073	23.33	0.17	23.33	0.17	1	0.0073	53.33	0.39
Cd	0.73	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mn	0.005475	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Zn	0.0219	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fe	0.0073	0	0	1	0.0073	0.67	4.89E-3	0	0	0.33	2.41E-3

Pb	0.219	0	0	0	0	10	2.19	20	4.38	10	2.19
NO ₃ ⁻	0.00438	19.2	0.084	18.2	0.0797	18.6	0.082	18.2	0.0797	18.6	0.082
SO ₄ ²⁻	0.000009	1.12	9.8E-6	0.94	8.23E-6	0.99	8.67E-6	0.96	8.41E-6	0.99	8.67E-6
PO ₃ ⁴⁻	0.00219	3.7	8.10E-3	6.5	0.014	3.6	7.88E-3	3.5	7.67E-3	3.7	8.10E-3
CL ⁻	0.0073	425	3.10	691.33	5.05	1030	7.52	1063	7.76	948.33	6.92
$\sum W_i = 1.0077$		$\sum q_i W_i = 3.35$		$\sum q_i W_i = 5.48$		$\sum q_i W_i = 10.16$		$\sum q_i W_i = 12.50$		$\sum q_i W_i = 9.85$	
WQI		3.32		5.44		10.08		12.40		9.77	

4. DISCUSSION

The results for physical and chemical properties of studied swimming pools are summarized in table 1. This is very important in the determination of its pollution status and thus general quality. The results obtained were compared with World Health Organization (WHO) and United State Environment Protection Agency (USEPA) Standard for recreational waters. All samples were colourless and having clear appearance. Only pool E appeared slightly cloudy, which could be due to dirt from its use by humans. At the time of sampling pool E, the pool was in use with an estimated number of about 40 users.

Temperature exerts a major influence on biological activity and growth. Temperature governs the kind of organisms that can live in swimming pools. The rate of chemical reactions generally increases at higher temperature. The temperature of the swimming pools studied ranged between 26.9±0.02 at pool B to 27.6±0.89 at pool E with mean of 27.18 which didn't conform to the normal range as prescribed by WHO/EPA (22-26) for recreational waters such as swimming pools.

The distribution of temperature during the study is introduced in figure 3. The distribution follows the trend: Pool E > Pool C = Pool A > Pool D > pool B. All swimming pool samples were outside the prescribed range. The time of sampling could be the reason for the temperature.

pH is a measure of how acidic/basic water is. The range goes from 0 - 14, with 7 being neutral. pH of less than 7 indicate acidity, whereas a pH of greater than 7 indicates a base. pH is really a measure of the relative amount of free hydrogen and hydroxyl ions in the water. Water that has more free hydrogen ions is acidic, whereas water that has more free hydroxyl ions is basic. Since pH can be affected by chemicals in the water, pH is an important indicator of water that is changing chemically. The pH of water determines the solubility (amount that can be dissolved in the water) and biological availability (amount that can be utilized by aquatic life) of chemical constituents such as nutrients (phosphorus, nitrogen, and carbon) and heavy metals (lead, copper, cadmium, etc.). In the case of heavy metals, the degree to which they are soluble determines their toxicity. Metals tend to be more toxic at lower pH because they are more soluble.

The pH obtained in the present study showed the pool were alkaline and ranges from 7.10±0.02 at pool B to 8.1±1.27 at pool E with mean of 7.72 which falls within the permissible range of 7.0 to 7.8 set by WHO/EPA for recreational waters. However, pool A and E showed

pH higher than the set limit. High pH in swimming pools has also been reported for swimming pools in Akwalbom and Cross River by Alfred and Mandu-Umeh, (2004). Under these circumstances, pH may have effects on the skin, eyes and hair condition by causing the hair fibres to swell and by cleaving the cystine bridges between adjacent polypeptide chains of hair protein (Agbagwa and Young–Harry, 2012). Consumption of high pH water could also lead to alkaliosis, which can result in coma (Enyoh *et. al.*, 2018). The distribution of pH in the studied swimming pools is presented in figure 3. The distribution follows the trend; pool B < pool C < pool D < pool A < pool E respectively.

Conductivity provides a measure of common salts (usually salts of calcium, sodium, magnesium, chlorides and fluorides) dissolved in water. A higher conductivity value indicates that there are more chemicals dissolved in the water. Because dissolved salts and other inorganic chemicals conduct electrical current, conductivity increases as salinity increases. Elevated dissolved solids can cause "mineral tastes" in drinking water. The conductivity of samples from this study ranged from $40 \pm 3.11 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to $80 \pm 3.44 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ which is very low when compared to the permissible limit of $1000 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ set by WHO. This is an indication that the swimming pools contain dissolved salt in little quantity. Similar observations were made for swimming pools in Kano metropolis by Indabawa *et. al.* (2015). The EC for the studied swimming pools follows the trend; pool A < pool C < pool B < pool D < pool E respectively (figure 4). The high EC recorded at E could be to the pool being in-use at the time of sampling. High EC have been reported for swimming pools after use (Indabawa *et. al.* 2015).

COD or Chemical Oxygen Demand is the total measurement of all chemicals (organics & in-organics) in the swimming pool water while BOD is a measure of, the amount of oxygen that is required for the bacteria to degrade the organic components present. The COD value ranged from 0.08 ± 0.07 at pool B to 1.02 ± 0.91 at pool A, while BOD value ranged from 0.03 ± 0.02 at pool A to 3.14 ± 0.13 at pool E. The mean of COD and BOD were 0.26 and 1.72 respectively. The results showed good swimming pool at pool B and C for BOD since it fell within the permissible limit of 1-2 set by WHO/EPA for recreation water. The remaining pools didn't fall within this range and thus showed poor water for BOD. The distribution of BOD and COD are presented in figure 5 to 6. The highest BOD was recorded at pool E while the highest COD was recorded at pool A. Similar results for BOD and COD have been reported by Alfred and Mandu-Umeh (2004).

Dissolved oxygen (DO), is the oxygen present in a dissolved form in a water body. It is labile and can be easily be reduced by carbon compounds to form carbon (IV) oxide (CO_2). It is generally related to the ability of a water body to hold aquatic life forms (Department of Water Affairs and Forestry, 1993). However, Dissolved oxygen level recorded here ranged from $3.9 \pm 1.77 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$ at pool B to $9.3 \pm 2.41 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$ at pool E with mean of $5.46 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$ which didn't meet WHO/EPA standard of 9-10 mg/kg for recreational waters. Low values of DO from the swimming pools have been reported (Alfred and Mandu-Umeh, 2004; Indabawa *et. al.*, 2015). Rapidly moving water, such as rivers tend to contain a lot of dissolved oxygen, whereas stagnant water contains less. In addition, the low DO recorded could be due to high temperature recorded for the swimming pools (Verla *et. al.*, 2018, Chong *et al.*, 2020). Only pool E showed good DO values while other pools showed low DO compared to standard (Figure 7)

Solids found in a water body exist as total, suspended, or dissolved. Some of these observed solids existed as suspended solids which ranged from $6.43 \pm 8.21 \text{ mg}/\text{l}$ at pool D to $42.44 \pm 7.00 \text{ mg}/\text{lat}$ pool E, which is lower than the set limit by WHO (50 mg/l). The trend of distribution followed the order; $E > C > A > B > D$ (figure 4.4). Similar trend was also observed

for total dissolved solids (TDS) (figure 8) which ranged from 22 ± 2.90 mg/l at pool D to 97.98 ± 8.79 mg/l at pool E. This also fell below the threshold of 500 mg/l set by WHO. The highest was recorded at pool E which follows highest EC. The result obtained here is very low when compared to result of 200 – 1500 mg/l for pools in Kano metropolis reported by Indabawa *et. al.*, (2015).

Macro elements are elements required in relatively large quantities for the normal physiological processes of the body. The macro element studied were Na, K, Mg, Ca with mean values of 0.41, 0.71, 0.07 and 0.05 respectively. The cations were lower than the set limit (table 1). The distributions for the major cations were presented in figures 9 to 10. In this present study, the anions analyzed were nitrate, sulphate, phosphate and chlorides. The results are presented in table 1 showing that nitrate ranged from 0.91 ± 0.02 mg/l to 0.96 mg/l with mean of 0.92 mg/l, sulphate ranged from 2.34 ± 0.10 mg/l to 2.81 ± 0.11 mg/l with mean 2.50 mg/l, phosphate ranged from 0.34 ± 0.02 mg/l to 0.65 ± 0.02 mg/l with mean 0.42 mg/l while chloride ranged from 12.75 ± 1.89 mg/l to 31.89 ± 2.04 mg/l with mean 24.23 mg/l. Except for chloride, all other studied anions were lower than the permissible limit set by WHO/EPA of 1-5 mg/l, 250 mg/l, 1-10 mg/l and 1-3 mg/l respectively which implies that the water is safe for use and in excess of chlorine. The excess chlorine could be from the use of chlorine to disinfect the swimming pools. A variety of disinfectants are used for pool water treatment. Those used most frequently in large, heavily used pools include chlorine, ozone and chlorine in combination and chlorine dioxide; less frequently used disinfectants include bromine and iodine. There are three main routes of exposure to chemicals in swimming pools or spa waters - inhalation of volatile or aerosolized solutes, dermal contact and direct ingestion of the water. For chlorine-based disinfectants, adequate routine disinfection should be achieved with a free chlorine residual level of at least 1 mg/litre throughout the pool. The distributions of studied anions in the different swimming pools are presented in figures 12 to 14.

4. 1. Heavy metals concentration

Heavy metals are elements having atomic weights between 63.546 and 200.590 and a specific gravity greater than 4.0. Living organisms require trace amounts of some heavy metals, including copper, iron, manganese and zinc etc. Excessive levels of essential metals, however, can be detrimental to the organism. Non-essential heavy metals of particular concern to surface water systems are cadmium and lead. All heavy metals exist in surface waters in colloidal, particulate, and dissolved phases, although dissolved concentrations are generally low. The solubility of trace metals in surface waters is predominantly controlled by the water pH, the type and concentration of ligands on which the metal could adsorb, and the oxidation state of the mineral components and the redox environment of the system.

However, in the present study heavy metals such as cadmium, manganese, and zinc were not detected in all studied swimming pools. Concentration of lead (Pb) ranged from ND at pool A, B to 0.002 ± 0.00 mg/l at pool D, iron (Fe) ranged from ND at pool A, D to 0.003 ± 0.00 mg/L at pool B. Copper (Cu) were detected in all samples which ranged from 0.003 mg/L at pool A to 0.16 mg/L at pool E. Comparing the mean values with WHO limit, all metals studied didn't exceed the threshold limit for water quality, indicating the water is unpolluted by these metals studied. This is good since ingestion of metals such as lead (Pb) and cadmium (Cd) may pose great risks to human health. Trace metals can interfere with essential nutrients in the body and causes small increases in blood pressure, severe damage to the brain and kidneys, damages nervous connections (Verla *et. al.*, 2017; Enyoh *et. al.*, 2018; Verla *et. al.*, 2018).

4. 2. Water Quality Index

The WQI in the present study is calculated from the physicochemical parameters of the borehole water samples and result presented in table 2. The computed WQI values are classified into five types as presented in table 3.1. The values from < 50 = Excellent water quality; 50-100 = Good water quality; 100-200 = Poor water quality; 200-300 = Very poor water quality; >300= Unsuitable for swimming. The individual indexes showed A (3.32), B (5.44), C (10.08), D (12.40) and E (9.77) with average WQI of 8.20 suggesting that the swimming pools is of “Excellent water quality”. Therefore, suggesting safe swimming pools for recreational activities. This could be due to time of sampling, good hygiene and proper maintenance of the pools by the management (Glauner et al., 2005, Amadi, 2012).

4. 3. Human Health risk

An individual risk pathway as a result of human exposure to trace metals contamination could be through inhalation via the nose and mouth and dermal absorption through the skin. Therefore, the average daily dose (ADD) due to exposure to heavy metals resulting from ingestion and dermal routes was computed using Eq. 9 and 10.

$$ADD_{Ingestion} = \frac{C_w \times RI \times FE \times DE}{B_w \times AT} \text{ in mg/kg/day} \tag{9}$$

$$ADD_{Dermal} = \frac{C_w \times SA \times K \times ABS \times ET \times FE \times EP \times CF}{B_w \times AT} \text{ in mg/kg/day} \tag{10}$$

where, ADD: average daily dose of metals (mg/kg/BWday); C_w: average concentration of the estimated metals in water (mg/kg); RI: ingestion rate is (2.2 L/day for adults; 1.8 L/day for children) obtained; FE: exposure frequency (365 days/year); DE: exposure duration (70 years for adults; and 6 years for children); B_w: average body weight (70 kg for adults; 15 kg for children); AT: averaging time (365 days/year × 70 years for an adult; 365 days/year × 6 years for a child) as described in earlier reports (Ibe et al., 2020). SA (18000 cm²) is the skin area available for contact, K (0.001 cm/hour) is the permeability coefficient, ABS (unit less) is the dermal absorption factor (0.001), ET (0.58 h/event) is the exposure time, CF (0.001 L/cm³) is the unit conversion factor (Amadi et al., 2010, Zeng et al., 2015).

Table 3. Average daily dose of heavy metals.

	Pathway	A		B		C		D		E	
		Adult	Child								
Cu	Ingestion	9.42E-4	3.6E-3	2.19E-3	8.4E-3	2.19E-3	8.4E-3	9.42E-5	3.6E-4	5.02E-3	1.92E-2
	Dermal	6.45E-7	3E-6	1.51E-6	7E-6	1.51E-6	7E-6	6.45E-8	3E-7	3.44E-6	1.6E-5
Cd	Ingestion	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Dermal	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Mn	Ingestion	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Dermal	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Zn	Ingestion	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Dermal	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Fe	Ingestion	-	-	5.02E-3	1.92E-2	6.28E-5	2.4E-3	-	-	3.14E-4	1.2E-4
	Dermal	-	-	3.44E-6	1.6E-5	4.3E-8	2E-7	-	-	2.15E-8	1E-7
Pb	Ingestion	-	-	-	-	3.14E-4	1.2E-4	6.28E-5	2.4E-3	3.14E-4	1.2E-4
	Dermal	-	-	-	-	2.15E-8	1E-7	4.3E-8	2E-7	2.15E-8	1E-7

The results for the average daily dose for heavy metals via ingestion and dermal pathway of exposure are presented in Table 3. All metals showed values of exposure pathways less than one indicating there were no high daily intake of heavy metals via the swimming pools. Values of dermal and ingestion exposure pathways are in agreement with those determined by Agomo and Amadi 2019, however values with regards to children for Cu and Fe were higher and could pose a danger.

5. CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded from this finding that some of the swimming pools did not conform to some parameters of WHO and EPA standard for recreational waters in terms of effectiveness of treatment of swimming pools especially pool E. However, the water quality index confirmed that the various swimming pools in Owerri municipal were of excellent quality even though there was high residual chlorine for all these pools. It is recommended that health authorities should regularly monitor the pools for compliance with regulations and frequency of treatment of these pools should also be intensified to minimize acute problems of swimming-associated illnesses. Further study should be conducted to check the quality of these pools before and after use.

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